

EMBEDDED TRILAYER GRAPHENE FLAKES UNDER INEFFICIENT TENSILE AND COMPRESSIVE LOADINGS

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ABSTRACT

The mechanical response of embedded ABA trilayer graphene flakes loaded in tension and compression on polymer beams is monitored by simultaneous Raman measurements through the strain sensitivity of the G or 2D peaks. A characteristic peculiarity of the investigated flake is that it contains a trilayer and bilayer part. The Bernal stacked bilayer was used as a strain sensor aiming to assess the efficiency of the load transfer from the polymer matrix through shear to the individual graphene layers. For the trilayer graphene in tension, both peaks are redshifted and splitting of the G peak is reported for the first time. In compression, the studied sample was an almost isolated trilayer, in which both peaks are blue-shifted up to a critical compressive strain. This critical strain is found to be one fourth of the value found in the case of single layer graphene despite the higher bending rigidity that trilayer exhibits over the much thinner monolayer.

1 INTRODUCTION

Ten years after the isolation and the characterization of graphene from A. Geim and K. Novoselov, graphene is still a very promising area of researcher. It is well known that graphene is a two dimensional crystal [1-4], showing unique and extraordinary mechanical properties. Its Young's modulus is estimated to be 1TPa and its strength is predicted to be 160 GPa [5, 6]. Additionally, it has been recently proved that the way, that monolayer (1LG) graphene lattices are stacked together to form bi-(2LG) and trilayer (3LG) graphene crystals, leads to the formation of new materials with unique electronic properties which are considerably different from those of the monolayer graphene [7-9].

On the other hand, trilayer graphene flakes are new area of interest and to our knowledge, only a few works have attempted to address the mechanical response of trilayer graphene either theoretically [10, 11] or experimentally [12]. Raman spectroscopy is a fast, sensitive and non-destructive technique and has been already used successfully to determine the stacking order of trilayer graphene samples. For specific excitation energy, ABA and ABC configurations have been distinguished by their different profile and the full-width-at-half-maximum of the corresponding 2D Raman peak [13, 14].

In the work of Gong et al. [12] the mechanical response of a trilayer graphene under axial tensile loading was examined through of the strain dependence of the 2D Raman peak. The maximum applied strain was 0.40%, and no evidence of G-mode splitting was observed for both 1LG and 2LG, which is the key phenomenon to ensure that uniaxial strain conditions have been imposed to the flake. Finally, in a subsequent publication by Gong et al [15] a clear evidence of Bernal stacking sequence distortion in few layer graphene upon axial tensile strain has been presented. The alterations in the 2D Raman profile caused by moderate axial strains of up to 0.4% were used to identify the loss of Bernal stacking in few layer graphene structures.

In general, the application of tensile stress induces phonon softening (red shift) whereas compressive stress causes phonon hardening (blue shift). Under uniaxial stress/ strain conditions, the double degeneracy of the E_{2g} phonon is lifted and the G peak splits in two components polarized parallel (G^- mode) and perpendicular (G^+ mode) to the strain axis [16, 17]. In very recent past, a number of authors have combined Raman Spectroscopy and mechanical measurements in order to examine the behaviour of monolayer graphene flakes (1LG) under tension [12, 16-24] and compression [17, 18]. The results have shown that there is a small variation of the slopes of G^- , G^+ (ranging between $\sim 30 - 34$ and $\sim 10 - 14$ $\text{cm}^{-1}/\%$, respectively), for uniaxial tensile [16, 18, 25] and compressive strains [18]. Theory predicts corresponding values to be ~ 30 and ~ 10 $\text{cm}^{-1}/\%$ [16, 26]. Moreover, the 2D peak strain sensitivity varies between $45 - 65$ $\text{cm}^{-1}/\%$ [16-18, 24, 25], with some samples showing also broadening and splitting of the peak [24, 25, 27]. The observation of 2D splitting depends on the excitation wavelength, the orientation of the graphene lattice along with the direction of strain with respect to incident/scattered light polarization [24, 25, 27-29]. Additionally, there are other parameters which affect the rates of G and 2D wavenumbers as a function of strain of 1LG such as: a) differences in the mechanical set ups, b) use of different substrates, e.g. PMMA, PET, PDMS, c) not efficient stress/ strain transfer and d) slippage of the flake during loading [12, 16-18, 21, 24]. Bilayer graphene (2LG) flakes and graphite in uniaxial tension have also been studied by us [19] and others [12] showing similar response to that observed for 1LG.

In this work, the mechanical response of mechanical exfoliated ABA trilayer graphene embedded into polymer substrates under tension and compression is presented by collecting simultaneously G and 2D Raman spectra at each strain level. [19]. In tension the extracted strain rates for both G and 2D peaks are found to be lower in value than previously reported [16-19], although they are similar for both bi- and trilayer parts of the same sample. In compression, the studied flake is an almost isolated trilayer and exhibits a response similar to that reported for the 1LG [30]. Both Raman peaks blue-shift up to a critical compressive strain and the corresponding strain rates within the elastic region of compressive strains are found lower than those expected [18, 30]. The results are discussed and compared with relevant works in the literature.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

Graphene bilayer and trilayer flakes were prepared by mechanical exfoliation from natural Kish graphite and transferred onto a PMMA- SU8 cantilever beam. After the deposition and the identification, a thin layer of PMMA photoresist was spin-coated on the top. Two different specimens were investigated, F1 and F2 as shown in ref [31]. Raman spectroscopy revealed that flake F1 contains a trilayer graphene (3LG) on top of a larger area of bilayer graphene (2LG). Flake F2 consists mainly of a large area 3LG and a graphite wedge formed during exfoliation from the transferring tape. Both examined trilayer flakes F1 and F2 are showing Bernal ABA stacking configuration, because at zero applied strain the amplitude of high intensity components is equal and thus the profile of 2D peak is more symmetric as opposed to the corresponding behaviour of the ABC stacking configuration [13, 14, 31, 32].

Raman spectra were measured at 785 nm (1.58eV) using a MicroRaman (InVia Reflex, Renishaw, UK) set-up. The laser power was kept below 1.2 mW on the sample to avoid laser induced local heating. A 100x objective with numerical aperture of 0.85 was used, and the spot size was estimated to be ~ 1.1 μm [33]. The polarization of the incident light was kept parallel to the strain axis. All Raman spectra were fitted using Lorentzian spectral functions.

For the uniaxial mechanical measurements, we used a single cantilever mechanical frame to induce the applied tensile and compressive strain to flakes monitoring simultaneously the response of the embedded samples. The top surface of the beam was subjected to tension and compression by flexing down and up the beam, respectively, by means of an adjustable screw positioned at a distance L from the fixed end. Raman spectra were collected at discrete values of applied strain. More information about the cantilever method is presented in references [17, 18].

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In sample F1 the Raman G peak of the Bernal stacked bilayer was used as a strain sensor in order to derive the actual strain transferred to the whole specimen [19]. Therefore, we performed a Raman mapping along a specific line at zero strain on the bilayer part in order to define residual strain distribution on the flake before tensile measurement [31]. From literature the value of Pos(G) for a bilayer graphene flake is estimated to be $\sim 1583.4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ [34-36]. The points all along the mapping line were found to redshift to values ranging from 1576.5 to 1583 cm^{-1} [31]. The residual strain at zero applied strain distributes from -0.02% (compressive) up to 0.12% (tensile) [16, 31] and results from the interaction with the substrate and the upper thin polymeric layer [17, 18, 35].

For the bilayer part of flake F1, the positions of G and 2D peaks shift both at lower wavenumbers under uniaxial tensile strains [31]. The onset of G splitting starts at $\sim 0.32\%$ (Fig. 1a), which is significantly higher than the 0.15% found in monolayer graphene samples [16]. The strain sensitivities of G^- and G^+ peak positions are measured to be -25.9 and $-9.7 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$, respectively. According to literature [12] the value of G^- component is lower, while the value for the G^+ is similar to that obtained in previous work [19]. Using a single Lorentzian component to fit the 2D peak, the rate was found to be $\sim -42.0 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$ (Fig. 1b). Moreover, it is well known that the 2D Raman peak of the bilayer graphene should be fitted by four [19, 37]. In our examined bilayer part the three lower frequency components, exhibit similar strain rates $-47.0 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$, while the higher frequency sub-peak shifts at a significantly lower rate of $-34.0 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$ [31]. The above strain rates are not again in agreement with the previous values reported in ref. [19].

Figure 1: a) Pos(G) and b) Pos(2D) as a function of uniaxial tensile strain for the bilayer part of the F1 flake.

For the ABA trilayer part of F1 sample G and 2D peaks are redshifted, linearly with strain (Fig. 2a,b). G peak splits into the G^- and G^+ components as expected [16, 17], and the onset of G splitting starts at $\sim 0.45\%$, which is again higher than the 0.15% found in monolayer graphene samples [16]. The strain rates of Pos(G^-) and Pos(G^+) components are -25.5 and $-12.6 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$, respectively, in accordance with the values of the bilayer part, indicating an homogeneous distribution of the interface between the flakes and the polymeric substrate along the F1 flake. The strain rate of 2D peak using a single Lorentzian component was found to be $\sim -43.0 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$, very close to the value that we have calculated for the bilayer part.

On the contrary, under compression, G and 2D peaks of flake F2 are blue shifted until -0.15% strain. After this strain level, both peaks are relaxed and at -0.4% strain a plateau is reached at wavenumber values of 1582 and 2635 cm^{-1} for Pos(G) and Pos(2D), respectively (Fig. 2a,b). For G peak no splitting is observed, and no significant change occurred to the profile of the 2D peak until the end of the measurement [14]. The strain rates for G and 2D peaks are 14.8 and 43.5 $\text{cm}^{-1}/\%$ until -0.15% strain, respectively. The response of an ABA trilayer graphene under compression resembles the behaviour of 1LG examined earlier [17, 18, 30]. The critical buckling

strain for the examined embedded trilayer was found to be -0.15% , which is four times lower than the value -0.6% found recently for 1LG [30]. According to theory, the critical strain to buckling is expected to be higher than monolayer graphene, because the bending stiffness in single layer graphene is three orders of magnitude lower. Two possible explanations could be a) the fact that the weakest interface is that between the inner graphene layers [15] and b) the cohesive failure between the layers during compression, process which is not take place in embedded monolayer graphene flakes. During compression, the polymer substrate and upper thin polymeric layer are deformed and the stress is transfer to the two outer graphene layers by interfacial stress, while the stress transfer to the inner layer only by shear from the two outer layers.

In addition, by comparing our results with other embedded bi- [12, 19] and trilayer graphene flake [12] from literature survey, we point out that all estimated strain rates are below the corresponding strain rates of G and 2D peak, respectively [14, 16, 23]. By taking into account that all flakes exhibit length greater than the needed critical transfer length [23], this indicates that the quality of the interface between graphene and polymer is poor. Moreover, the architecture of the embedded flake (isolated flake or being part of a flake) may have a significant contribution in the strain rates of both G and 2D peaks and consequently in the mechanics of the model composites [31].

Figure 2: a) The Pos(G) and b) the Pos(2D) under uniaxial compressive and tensile strains for flakes F1, and F2.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Bernal stacked bilayer and ABA trilayer graphene parts embedded in polymer beams were studied under uniaxial tensile and compressive loadings. During tensile measurement, bilayer part of flake F1 was used as a strain sensor. For bilayer and trilayer parts of flake F1, the G peak splits into G^- and G^+ components and the onset of splitting was observed at higher strain levels than those found in literature for monolayer graphene layers. The strain rates of G and 2D peaks of both parts are quite similar, indicating that the quality of the interface between flake and polymer is almost the same throughout the whole flake. In compression, both G and 2D peaks of trilayer flake F2 were shifted linearly to higher wavenumbers until -0.15% strain, where they start relaxing to their zero strain values due to the out-of-plane buckling failure mode. This value of critical strain is much smaller than the value found for monolayer graphene flakes [33]. Moreover, the corresponding strain rates for G and 2D peaks until -0.15% were found lower than those expected.

Finally, the reduced strain rates found in this work for G and 2D peaks indicate that both samples F1 and F2 are under inefficient tensile and compressive loadings. Moreover, taking into account the architecture of the investigated samples, it is concluded that by tailoring the morphology of a few layer graphene the quality of the graphene/polymer interface will be

significantly improved. Further work regarding efficient reinforcing of graphene based nanocomposites will be presented in a future work.

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